

EFFECTS OF PEER TUTORING ON ORAL READING FLUENCY AMONG STRUGGLING READERS OF JUNIOR HIGHSCHOOL

Chavez, A., Sinadjan, H., Soronio, R., Vallermosa, S., Dinagsao, Y., Quimbo, R. (2025)
College of Teacher Education - Generalist

Abstract

Fluency in oral reading is essential for literacy and is the foundation of academic achievement, especially for junior high school student. A good reader is characterized by their reading fluency. On the other hand, poor readers are distinguished by their inability to read fluently. Peer tutoring has emerged as a potential intervention to support these learners by providing assistance and fostering a collaborative learning environment. This study investigates the Effects of Peer tutoring on oral reading fluency in struggling readers of Junior High School students. This research uses a mixed-method approach, the study involved 17 students who participated in oral reading fluency. Quantitative data were gathered using the Project LETRA tool, which assessed word, sentence and paragraph levels, including miscues. Qualitative data captured students' perceptions, emotional responses, and observed improvements in oral reading fluency. Thematic analysis reveals six major themes which has a positive and negative theme these are: Positive (Vocabulary development, Cognitive development, fluency) Negative (Seld-consciousness, word and pronunciation difficulty and distractions). The findings indicate that peer tutoring significantly enhance oral reading fluency, with notable improvements in vocabulary development, cognitive development and fluency. However, some challenges were identified including, self-consciousness, word and pronunciation difficulty and distraction. Despite these challenges, participation in peer tutoring positively influenced both academic and emotional aspects of reading, fostering greater confidence and motivation among students.

Keywords: accuracy, oral reading fluency, peer tutoring, speed, struggling readers, tutee, tutor

Introduction

As people progress through adolescence, they slowly realize the importance of reading. Fluency in oral reading is essential for literacy and is the foundation of academic achievement, especially for junior high school student. A good reader is characterized by their reading fluency. On the other hand, poor readers are distinguished by their inability to read fluently. Children who struggle with reading in primary school are more likely to suffer through high school (Roberts et al., 2022), which puts them at high risk of dropping out (Hernandez, 2011). Learning and development trajectories can be negatively impacted by reading challenges. Ineffective fluency abilities make it difficult for readers to translate spoken sounds into written

language and back again (Langdon, 2004). As a result, their personal vocabulary is small, which hinders effective comprehension (Torgeson, 2000). Some reading disabilities are associated with a deficiency in word recognition fluency (Moyer, 2001).

According to a recent study, students are more likely to acquire knowledge when they have stronger reading abilities (Akbash, 2011). The ability to read is critical for opening knowledge spaces, in such a way that public authorities around the world have focused on promoting reading practices and skills starting in early childhood education (Mullis and Martin, 2015). The most advantageous results, children at risk of reading failure should be identified and screened early with measures that assess

important reading skills such as: alphabetic understanding, phonological awareness and automaticity (Kame'enui, et al., 2000).

Oral reading fluency is one of the five fundamental components of literacy and is a necessary condition for autonomous text comprehension (National reading panel, 200). It is simpler for a student to understand a material when they read it with the right speed, precision and expression since they can concentrate on it (Raspica, 2013). Fluent readers tend to have more positive attitudes towards reading, as well as a more positive perception of themselves as readers. Unfortunately, oral reading fluency is frequently neglected by classroom teachers who may feel pressed to spend more time working on comprehension tasks and not devote sufficient time to practicing oral reading of connected texts (NRP, 2000; Topping, 2006)

Reading fluency is a crucial aspect of literacy development (Rasinski, 2006), but reading fluency has been ignored in reading instruction (Kuhn, 2004). According to studies showing a link between oral reading fluency and reading comprehension, school administrator and teachers need to actively work toward improving students reading fluency (Rasinski, 2004), but there are many reasons why it has been neglected. The integration of fluency teaching into the reading curriculum was never taught to teachers (Richards, 2000). Without specific coaching, struggling readers might not become fluent on their own. (Hudson et al., 2005). Most teachers concentrate on accuracy and comprehension, so oral reading fluency seems to be the missing piece in their reading instruction (Vaughn et al, 2004). Basal readers require teachers to concentrate on word recognition, vocabulary growth, and comprehension while ignoring oral fluency (Zutell et al 1991).

Junior high school students are exposed to more challenging reading texts that call for effective word decoding while preserving comprehension. They could feel frustrated, unmotivated, and unconfident when reading if they are not fluent enough. Their overall literacy development and academic performance may suffer long-term consequences as a result of this difficulty. Because of this, academics and educators are still looking for ways to help pupils improve their reading fluency. According to research, teachers should give students lots of chances to practice reading, ideally with the help of more proficient readers (teachers, peers, or parents) who can offer feedback on the readings and assist students in recognizing and fixing their errors. (Zimmermann et al, 2021).

Peer-mediated treatments, which include using other students as change agents, could be a useful way to give kids practice with tasks that will help them become more fluent in fundamental academic abilities like oral reading. (Hoff & Robinson, 2002). It is an interactive, methodical, and significant procedure that is frequently employed one-on-one, that is, amongst peers, when more experienced students—not necessarily teachers—assist less experienced students. (Topping et al., 2016). Peer learning has received a lot of attention in a variety of fields, including science, languages, mathematics, and educational stages. (Johnson & Johnson, 2010). Peer tutoring is widely acknowledged as a crucial component of Western universities and colleges, greatly enhancing students' academic performance. (Takeuchi (2015)). The idea that students may teach and learn from one another is commonly accepted as beneficial.

Recent research studies highlight the impact of peer tutoring on the development of key aspects of reading competence: comprehension, speed, precision, fluency and self-esteem (Miller,

et al, 2010). The pair has a common and shared goal that has to be achieved within an interactive framework previously planned by the teacher (Duran & Vidal, 2014). The benefits of peer tutoring are evident and widely recognized. On the one hand, tutors own learning process is aided by the specific task of teaching other students (Cortese, et al). On the other hand, tutees profit from the adapted and personalized aids that tutors offer them (Robinson, et al, 2005).

This is also reinforced by other theories that readers will have difficulty understanding the contents of the reading if they are not given effective reading instructions (Macleod & van der Veen, 2020; Mahan, 2022). Peer tutoring has a strong effect in teaching reading comprehension of narrative text (Roma et al. (2019)0. The majority of students in learning to read prefer to ask the teacher if something is not understood. They will lose interest in reading if they don't inquire. Of course, this is bad if it's done all the time. Instead, a method that can help pupils reach their own knowledge through the material they read is required. (Myers, 1991; Susantini et al., 2021).

All of the previously described strategies have been shown to be effective in improving elementary-aged readers' fundamental and non-disabled reading skills. (Kuhn, 2005; et al.,). However, few studies have shown equal benefits with struggling adolescent readers (Wexler, et al. 2008). The purpose of this study is to look into how peer tutoring affects junior high school student's oral reading fluency. It seeks to ascertain whether students' reading accuracy, speed, and prosody may be considerably enhanced by this teaching strategy. The study will also investigate what is the effect of peer tutoring on the students. The results of this study, which looks at how well peer tutoring works as a reading intervention, can add to the body of knowledge already available in literacy

education and offer insightful information to educators.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of peer tutoring on oral reading fluency in struggling readers of Junior High School.

This study answered the central question: The effects of peer tutoring on oral reading fluency of the struggling readers of Junior High School, specifically it would answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of oral reading fluency among Junior High School students struggling readers before peer tutoring?
2. What is the level of oral reading fluency of the students after peer tutoring?
3. What is the effect of Peer tutoring on the oral reading fluency of Junior High School student struggling readers?
4. Is there a significant difference between the student's oral reading fluency before and after conducting peer tutoring?

Methods

This study used a concurrent mixed method, which entails gathering and evaluating both quantitative and qualitative data (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018) to discover the effects of peer tutoring on oral reading fluency in struggling readers of junior high school students. Combining these approaches yields quantifiable results as well as more profound understanding of children's reading experiences and growth.

For the quantitative method the descriptive-correlational design is used in this study to determine if there is a significant relationship between peer tutoring and the oral reading fluency by gathering numerical data. Correlational research involves measuring the degree of association between two or more variables without manipulating them (Creswell,

2012). This design is suitable to determine and discover the relationship of peer tutoring and oral reading fluency. Descriptive- correlational research is ideal for identifying the characteristic of a particular group and examining possible relationships among variables. (Fraenkel, et al., 2012).

For the qualitative method researcher used the phenomenological research design to investigate the real-life experiences of junior high school students who took part in peer tutoring sessions and struggled with reading. In order to better understand how students view, feel, and interpret their tutoring experience particularly with regard to their reading difficulties, motivation, and emotional reactions this approach was chosen. Phenomenology focuses on the essence of human experiences are perceived by participants, allowing the researcher to gather rich, detailed accounts of individual experiences (Creswell, 2013). Finding common themes among participants is a key component of phenomenological research, which aims to explain the shared significance of the experiences (Moustakas, 1994).

This study was conducted in one of the private schools located at Zamboanga del Sur a private school. The school has both secondary (junior high school and senior high school) and college-level students. The researcher selected only the junior high school students where the peer tutoring is conducted to assist struggling readers. It mainly includes (17) Junior High School Students; Six (6) Grade 7 students Section Dalia, One (1) Grade 7 students Section Rose, Two (2) Grade 8 students Section Lily, One (1) Grade 8 student Section Tulip, Two (2) Grade 8 students Section Daisy, Five (5) Grade 10 students Section Cattleya.

The study participants were the struggling readers of junior high school students from one of the private schools

located Zamboanga del Sur who undergo peer tutoring. In total, seventeen students took part in the research, representing different grade levels within the junior high school. Seven were from the Grade 7, five were from Grade 8 and another 5 from Grade 10.

The participants should be students enrolled in junior high school of one of the private schools in Zamboanga del Sur. who are struggling readers and who have undergone peer tutoring intervention. Participants in the analysis and reporting of results are given code names in order to preserve anonymity and guarantee structured data presentation. For Example: P1 refers to Participant 1 and P2 refers to Participants 2, and so on. These codes will be used consistently to secure participant identity and provide clear data interpretation throughout the transcribing, thematic analysis, and discussion of findings. Lastly, these students must also be willing to give their full consent to serve as participants of the study. Before the conduct of the study, the researcher made sure that all of the aforementioned requirements were satisfied prior to starting the investigation.

The participants were chosen using the purposive sampling, a kind of non-probability sampling technique where participants are chosen based on their availability and willingness to participate, as part of their purposive sampling strategy. The sample consisted of junior high school students who were readily accessible to the researchers and who met the basic criteria of being classified as struggling readers. This method was chosen due to practical considerations, such as time constraints and the accessibility of participants within the school setting. Although convenience sampling may limit the generalizability of the findings, it is commonly used in educational research where obtaining a fully randomized sample is not feasible (Etikan, et al., 2016).

The study used is adapted from project LETRA (*Language Enhancement through Reading Assessment*) Survey Questionnaire and the IGQ (Interview guide questionnaire) as well as a passage taken from Phil- Iri Tool entitled “Dark Chocolate”. Together, these tools produced the descriptive and numerical data needed for analysis. English grammar experts confirmed the validity of the instrument. The survey questionnaire is adapted from Project LETRA it consists of four parts. The first part is the student’s profile to know if they participated in peer tutoring. The second part is the oral reading fluency assessment using project LETRA with three levels. Word level, Sentence level and Paragraph level which collectively assess the student’s reading accuracy, fluency, and type of miscues. Data collected from this tool include the number of words and sentences read, the types of frequency of miscues, the performance in paragraph reading. This tool provided a structured and systematic way to monitor progress and identify specific areas of improvement.

Finally, an interview guide was used to collect qualitative data, the researcher made an interview guide questions to explore the students’ thoughts, feelings, challenges and improvements about peer tutoring. Instead of oral interviews, students were asked to write their responses in the spaces provided after each question. This allowed them to express their answers in writing at their own pace. The collected responses were analyzed using a phenomenological approach to better understand their lived experiences during the intervention.

In gathering the necessary data, the researcher was trained by their adviser on the proper utilization of project LETRA. This ensured that the researchers were knowledgeable about the objectives and procedure of the program. Next the researcher obtained formal approval from the Principal’s Office, the School

Academic Head, and the Research Coordinator in one of the private schools in Zamboanga del sur and proceed with the study. Once granted authorization, the researchers submitted the research instrument for expert validation to ensure its content was relevant, reliable, and appropriate for the selected respondents. Following the validation process, the researchers formally requested permission from the class advisers of Junior High School to conduct the survey among identified struggling readers who were participating in peer tutoring sessions. The participants were purposively selected from six different sections, consisting of a total of 17 students—13 boys and 4 girls—who were officially enrolled one of the private schools in Molave. Upon receiving full clearance and coordinating with the class advisers, the researchers administered the survey within the school setting. The participants were first oriented on the purpose and procedures of the study. They were then given 20 to 25 minutes to engage in a guided reading session and complete a questionnaire specifically designed to assess their oral reading fluency and examine the effect of peer tutoring strategies. This approach allowed for an organized and timely collection of the completed instruments. The data gathered were then carefully tallied, processed, analyzed, and interpreted to determine the effectiveness of peer tutoring in improving the oral reading fluency of struggling Junior High School students.

In this study, researchers employed both descriptive statistics and the paired sample t-test to analyzed the data collected from our participants. Descriptive statistics are statistics used to meaningfully summarize and arrange data, offering insights into the features of the sample. They consist of measurements of variability (range/standard deviation) and central tendency (mean, median, mode) (Bhandari, 2023). These statistics provide a clear summary of the facts, allowing

comprehension without drawing conclusions outside of the available data. To ascertain whether there is a significant difference between the means of two related groups, statisticians employ the paired sample t-test, also called the dependent sample t-test (Kent State University Libraries.). When the same individuals are measured in two separate settings, such as before and after an intervention, this test is suitable. The statistical analyses were carried out using the Jamovi software (The Jamovi project 2023), which facilitated accurate computation and interpretation of the results. These statistical techniques allowed the collected data to be thoroughly and properly evaluated.

Result and Discussion

This section showed the oral reading fluency results of Junior High School students who struggled with reading both before and after receiving peer tutoring.

Table 1.
The level of oral reading fluency of struggling readers before peer tutoring.

	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Oral reading fluency before peer tutoring	17	50.6%	23.1%	Very low

Scales: 90-100% Very High, 85-89% High, 84-80 Moderate, 79-75% Low, 74% and below Very low

Table 1 reveals that the oral reading fluency of the struggling readers of junior high school student before peer tutoring is ($M= 50.6, SD=23.1$), and it was *very low*. This shows that before peer tutoring session the student's oral reading fluency is extremely low.

The result suggests that the participants who are the struggling readers had significant difficulties with oral reading fluency prior to peer tutoring. With a mean score of 50.6, these students were often performing much below the predicted level of fluency in oral reading. There was a broad variety of performance levels among the participants, as seen by the comparatively large standard deviation of 23.1; some may have performed somewhat

better than the group average, while others fell much further below.

Oral reading fluency is a critical component of reading competence and is closely linked to comprehension (Rasinski 2012) A low fluency score may indicate that students are still developing foundational decoding skills and may face difficulties in understanding what they read due to slow or inaccurate reading.

Table 2.
The level of oral reading fluency of struggling readers after peer tutoring.

	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Oral reading fluency after peer tutoring	17	86.1%	5.42%	High

Scales: 90-100% Very High, 85-89% High, 84-80 Moderate, 79-75% Low, 74% and below Very Low

Table 2 shows the level of oral reading fluency of the struggling readers of junior high school students after peer tutoring is ($M=86.1, SD= 5.42$) and base on the interpretation scale, these scores fall within the high category.

Participants' oral reading fluency significantly improved, as evidenced by the significant rise from the pre-test mean of 50.6 to the post-test mean of 86.1. Furthermore, the fact that the standard deviation dropped from 23.1 to 5.42 indicates that students' scores stabilized following the intervention. As a result, there was a decrease in individual scores and the group's overall performance levels improved. Peer tutoring sessions resulted in a significant increase in oral reading fluency, as evidenced by the improvement in the average score and the consistency of the students' performance. This post-test information sheds light on the struggling readers' development in comparison to their initial performance. Guided and repeated reading interventions, such as peer tutoring, significantly improve fluency by providing learners with immediate feedback and opportunities for repeated practice. (Kuhn et al, 2010).

Table 3.
Paired Sample T-Test Results Significant Difference of Oral Reding Fluency Before and After Peer Tutoring

Comparison	Mean Before	Mean After	t-value	df	p-value	Significance
Oral reading fluency (Before vs After)	50.6%	86.1%	-7.14	16	<.001	Positive

Table 3 presents the data using the paired sample t-test (also called dependent samples t-test) is a statistical test used to compare two related measurements usually before and after from the same group of people or subjects). The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores, $t(16) = -7.14$, $p < .001$. We reject the null hypothesis since the p-value is below the traditional significance level of 0.05. This indicates that peer tutoring had a significant positive effect on improving students' oral reading fluency. In summary, the data strongly support the conclusion that peer tutoring is an effective intervention for enhancing oral reading fluency among struggling readers of junior high school students. Peer tutoring provides struggling readers with frequent opportunities for guided practice and immediate feedback, both of which are essential for developing oral reading fluency.

After examining the quantitative results through descriptive statistics and paired sample t-test, it became essential to explore the students' deeper experiences to gain a richer understanding of how peer tutoring affected students beyond measurable outcomes, the study employed Thematic analysis, one of the popular techniques in qualitative research for finding, examining, and summarizing patterns (themes) in data. One of the most popular strategies in qualitative psychology and social science research nowadays is this methodical and approachable technique (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This approach is especially useful when researchers want to learn about experiences, viewpoints, or actions directly from the participants. Through theme analysis, the researchers are able to determine the possible concept behind the data. The study results revealed that peer tutoring had notable effects on the students oral reading fluency, which were organized

into six major themes with positive and negative themes, namely: Positive: a.) Vocabulary development, b.) Cognitive Development, c.) Fluency. And for negative theme: d.) Sel- Consciousness e.) Word and Pronunciation Difficulty f.) Distraction.

Effects of peer tutoring on oral reading fluency on the struggling readers of junior high school

Vocabulary development

Reading is one of the most effective ways to improve vocabulary. It is the process of expanding and enhancing one's range of words, phrase, and expressions. It involves learning new words and understanding their meanings and incorporating them into speech and writing. It helps in effective communication making it easier to express thoughts clearly. 4 out of 17 participants answered that their vocabulary developed. These are their responses:

"I like it because it helps with my studies." P5

"I'm happy because I learned" P8

"I felt a bit nervous at first, but now the nervousness is gone. I feel happy because I've learned some new words." P10

"I have learned new words that are nice to read." P11

Some of the best strategies for vocabulary development encourage students to discuss words and provide readings of materials that familiarize students with a large range of high-level words (Marie Carbo (2005). Developing one's vocabulary improves cognitive abilities including reasoning and thinking (Demir, et al 2006). As cognitive abilities like understanding, learning, and critical thinking improve, vocabulary becomes a

more important indicator of academic achievement (Bishop et al., 2009). Students who have a strong vocabulary in a certain academic discipline are better able to comprehend and articulate the ideas and concepts that are distinctive to that field. Thus, the complexity of students' academic language is directly related to their academic success (Bishop et al., 2009). Students that have a large vocabulary are better able to connect 78 cooperative terms with more general ideas, which promotes deeper comprehension and improved academic performance.

Cognitive Development

Students' descriptions of gaining new knowledge, developing deeper comprehension, improving their skills, and being more motivated to interact with academic material all demonstrated the theme of learning. Numerous students emphasized how techniques like guided oral reading, group projects, and peer tutoring contributed to the development of a friendly and engaging atmosphere that increased the accessibility and significance of learning. By using these techniques, students were able to exchange ideas, clear up misconceptions, and reinforce teachings through social contact, which improved the effectiveness and engagement of the learning process. By means, four out of seventeen students claimed that they learned by the oral reading techniques. These are their responses.

"I learned to read the words and understand the words because she is teaching me how to read". P6

"I learned how to read." P7

"I learned how to read." P8

"I learned some words and new words." P10

"I learned new meaning of words." P11

"I learned new words while reading." P13

"I understand letters that is difficult for me to understand".P15

Peer tutoring introduced children to modeling, corrective feedback, and regular reading practice—all of which are shown to enhance quantifiable learning results. Peer learning situations like these help students solidify their knowledge through instruction and engagement, which speeds up the acquisition of new skills (Topping, 2005). In this setting, increases in fluency and reading speed and accuracy became discernible indicators of cognitive growth, which are essential components of literacy development and reading comprehension.

Furthermore, students' perceptions of themselves changed as they improved their reading accuracy and fluency, starting to believe that they were competent students. This is consistent with Vygotsky's (1978) idea of the Zone of Proximal Development, which states that students can complete tasks they couldn't complete on their own with the assistance of more experienced peers. As a result, peer tutoring produces reading improvements that go beyond academic achievement; they reflect a deeper internalization of reading processes and the conviction that learning is taking place.

Fluency

Throughout the intervention, participants often reported how their reading, speaking, and self-expression skills in English had significantly improved. The results showed that exercises like peer tutoring, oral reading practice, and repeated exposure to vocabulary and sentence structures were essential for improving students' fluency. As they practiced speaking more easily in a less scary setting through peer interactions, learners stated that regular reading aloud helped them improve their pronunciation, rhythm, and tempo. In class conversations and reading assignments,

many students reported feeling more comfortable speaking English, stating that the more they practiced, the more proficient they were. This are the following responses of the participants.

“Yes, I can read faster” P9

*“I became faster at reading the words.”*P15

“My reading speed improved.” P17

An important component of the pupils’ reading progress after engaging in peer tutoring. Many participants reported enhanced expression, easier reading, and smoother pacing—all essential elements of oral reading fluency. They observed that frequent reading practice with classmates helped students become less hesitant and increased their automaticity in word recognition, which is a crucial component of fluent reading. Includes the capacity to read a text accurately, rapidly, and expressively. Peer tutoring gave children the chance to practice reading repeatedly with guidance, which is crucial for improving fluency, according to study. Peer tutoring’s collaborative atmosphere promoted regular oral reading so that students could get feedback and see how their colleagues read fluently. Students’ shift from laborious, sluggish decoding to more certain and expressive reading was greatly aided by this interactive practice setting. Rasinski (2012):

Self-Consciousness

During activities that required oral engagement, such reading aloud, speaking in front of the class, or participating in peer conversations, many students showed emotions of hesitancy and nervousness. Frequently, this anxiety resulted from a lack of confidence in their linguistic abilities, a fear of making mistakes, or a concern of being evaluated by their peers. Many participants reported that they experienced pressure to accomplish tasks in front of others, which impacted their

focus and performance. The following were common responses of our participants.

“Nervous.” P2

“Nervous.” P4

“Got nervous while reading.”

“P9

“I felt a bit nervous at first, but now the nervousness is gone. I feel happy because I’ve learned some new words.” P10

“I got nervous because they made me read.” P14

“I was nervous.” P12

“I got nervous while reading.” P16

*“I got nervous because I though there are difficult questions.”*P17

Those that read aloud, especially language learners, frequently experience severe anxiety because they fear receiving a poor grade. Often, this anxiety is made worse by the fear of making mistakes or of receiving negative feedback from classmates or teachers. Brown (2019). Reading fluency and general performance can be hampered by elevated anxiety, which is frequently caused by a fear of receiving a poor grade (Young, 1991). In these circumstances, language learners, in particular, experience increased stress since they are frequently more self-conscious about their ability and the possibility of making mistakes. One of the main causes of anxiety when performing oral reading activities is the worry of mispronouncing words. Students frequently fear that giving the wrong pronunciation will make them seem less competent, which feeds a vicious cycle of anxiety that only makes their reading performance worse (Javid 2014). Because of this worry, people may read more slowly, have trouble pronouncing words correctly, or even steer clear of oral reading exercises entirely. Fluency is hampered by the fear of making a mistake, which also

prevents the learner from giving the reading material their whole attention.

Word and Pronunciation Difficulty

Experiences that pupils have when reading, especially with regard to fluency, pronunciation, comprehension, and decoding. These challenges, which can be major roadblocks to advancement, are frequently more noticeable for readers who are developing or learning a second language. These are the common responses of the participants.

"I read slowly, I'm not very good at reading, but sometimes I'm just really slow and I can't pronounce some words". P1

"Not very fast". P4

"I can't pronounce the words very well" P9

"Not really." P16.

"I encountered difficult words because of peer tutoring, and my reading speed improved." P5

"The words are difficult." P17

Appeared often in the students' analyses of their reading experiences. Many participants mentioned that they had trouble pronouncing new words correctly, decoding words, and sustaining understanding, especially while reading aloud. These issues frequently caused them to read more slowly, pause more frequently, and lack confidence, all of which hampered their general fluency and interaction with the material. Because they were afraid of mispronouncing words or of receiving negative feedback from their peers, a number of pupils experienced anxiety when reading aloud. Studies show that language learners frequently suffer from anxiety while reading aloud because they are afraid of making mistakes, particularly with spelling, Javid's (2014).

Such emotional strain might interfere with reading comprehension and lead to chronic avoidance practices.

Distraction

Many of the struggling readers appeared to have difficulty maintaining focus while reading often getting sidetracked by external noises, question activities, or even their own thoughts. This lack of concentration disrupted their ability to read fluently, leading to frequent pauses, hesitations, and errors such as mispronunciations, skipped words or repetition. These behaviors reflected a general sense of disengagement and lack of confidence, which hindered their overall reading progress. These are their following responses.

"My classmates are so noisy". P2

"I can't focus because they keep on talking, I will not listen to them." P4

"I can't focus." P16

"I listen but my classmates are so noisy." P7

"I was a bit stressed because of the noise, but I focused." P15

A typical difficulty that students encounter when participating in peer tutoring sessions. Many participants stated that background distractions that were not controlled throughout the session, motions in the room, or close students conversing frequently interfered with their ability to concentrate on reading and learning. Students found it challenging to focus and remain involved in the task at hand because of these other influences. Some students mentioned social disruptions in addition to environmental ones, such as when tutors or tutees get distracted, start irrelevant discussions, or act casually during class. These actions caused time to be wasted and distracted from the academic emphasis. Distractions in classrooms, especially ones

with no structure or discipline, might cause students to become less motivated and perform worse academically (Wentzel and Brophy, 2014). Unmanaged distractions can quickly compromise the attention span, stability, and clear instructional focus that are essential to peer tutoring's efficacy.

The combined analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data shows how peer tutoring significantly contributed to students' improvement in reading. The improvement in their oral reading from 50.6% before the intervention to 86.1% after, shows clear progress, supported statistically by the results of the paired t-test. At the same time, the six qualitative themes, three positive (Vocabulary development, Cognitive development, fluency) and three negative (Self-consciousness, Word and Pronunciation difficulty and distractions) offer valuable insights into students experiences in peer tutoring. These two methods help researcher understand that by participating in peer tutoring it improves both the academic and emotional aspects of reading.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The findings of this study clearly demonstrate that peer tutoring significantly improves oral reading fluency among junior high school struggling readers. Both quantitative and qualitative data revealed that students experienced notable growth in vocabulary acquisition, reading speed, word recognition, and comprehension. The pre- and post-test comparison showed a statistically significant difference, indicating that peer tutoring is an effective intervention for enhancing oral reading fluency. From the qualitative analysis, themes such as vocabulary development, learning, fluency, and understanding highlighted the students' learning progress and emotional responses. Despite facing challenges like distractions and difficulties with pronunciation, students still exhibited

improvement in reading performance and confidence.

Therefore, this study concludes that peer tutoring is a valuable, effective, and accessible intervention for helping struggling readers develop oral reading fluency necessary for academic success.

Based on the findings mentioned above the researchers endorse the following recommendations:

1. The researchers strongly advised students to take the initiative to evaluate their reading fluency since knowing one's strengths and areas for development is a crucial first step in developing reading confidence. Seeking help is a show of resolve to get better, not a sign of weakness. Fluency, confidence, and a more positive attitude about reading may all be greatly improved by regularly practicing reading with others.
2. Researcher recommend educators to evaluate their students oral reading fluency to measure the student's current level particularly at the start of each school year. Determining the student's level can help teachers know who are the struggling readers and fluent readers and they can implement peer tutoring if there are students who lack reading skills. Knowing this ahead of time can make informed decisions about how to pair students effectively.
3. The administrator can implement a peer tutoring intervention by scheduling 30-minute sessions three days a week, ensuring that students have regular, focused opportunities to improve their reading fluency.
4. Future researchers are recommended to investigate how peer tutoring affects reading fluency over the long run, especially when considering multiple grade levels or reading skill levels. Future research could examine the effects of particular tutoring techniques or various tutor-tutee combinations on

results, possibly revealing the best methods.

References

- Agustine, D., Arvianti, I., & Heriyanto, E. (2022). The improvement of mispronunciation encountered by most young English learners. *Jurnal CULTURE (Culture, Language, and Literature Review)*, 9(1), 94–118. <https://doi.org/10.53873/culture.v9i1.243>
- Beach, K. D., and Traga Philippakos, Z. A. (2021). 'Effects of a summer reading intervention on the reading performance of elementary grade students from low-income families. *Read. Writ. Q.* 37, 169–189. Doi: 10.1080/10573569.2020.1760154
- Bhandari, P. (2021, July 15). Questionnaire Design: Methods, Question Types & Bhandari, P. (2023, June 21). Descriptive Statistics | Definitions, Types, Examples. Scribbr. Retrieved March 17, 2025, from <https://www.scribbr.com/statistics/descriptive-statistics/> Examples. Scribbr.
- Blanch, S., Duran, D., Flores, M., and Valdebenito, V. (2012). 'The effects of a peer tutoring programme to improve the reading comprehension competence involving primary students at school and their families at home'. *Proc. Soc. Behav. Sci.* 46, 1684–1688. Doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.05.361
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Brown, L. T. (2019). *Cognition and communication: How we interpret language*. Mind Works Publishing.
- Bruner, J. S. (1996). *The culture of education*. Harvard University Press.
- Carbo, M. (2005). *Becoming a great teacher of reading: Achieving high rapid reading gains with powerful, differentiated strategies*. Corwin Press.
- Cartledge, G., Gardner, R. III, & Ford, D. (2009). *Diverse learners with exceptionalities: Culturally responsive teaching in the inclusive classroom*. Columbus, OH: Pearson.
- Casanova, M. P. (2012). "O Papel da 82ooperat ao serviço do desenvolvimento curricular [paper presentation]," in *Proceedings of the XIX 82ooperat da AFIRSE "revisitar os estudos curriculares: Onde estamos e para onde vamos?"*. (Lisboa: EDUCA/Secção Portuguesa da AFIRSE).
- Chall, J.S., & Jacobs, V.A. (2003). The classic study on poor children's fourth grade slump. *American Educator*, 21, 14-15.
- Clark, H. H. (1996). *Using language*. Cambridge University Press.
- Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive Science*, 12(2), 257–285. Schunk, D. H., Pintrich, P. R., & Meece, J. L. (2014).

- Cole, M. W. (2013). *Rompiendo el Silencio: Meta-analysis of the effectiveness of peer-mediated learning at improving language outcomes for ELLs*. *Bilingual Research Journal*, 36(2), 146–166.
- Cole, M. W. (2014). *Speaking to read: Meta-analysis of peer-mediated learning for English language learners*. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 46(3), 358–382
- Cooc, N., & Kim, J. S. (2016). “Peer Influence on Children’s Reading Skills: Social Network Analysis of Elementary School Classrooms.” *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 109 (5) :727-740.
- Cooc, N., & Kim, J. S. (2016). “Peer Influence on Children’s Reading Skills: Social Network Analysis of Elementary School Classrooms.” *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 109 (5) :727-740.
- Cortese, A. D. (2005). Peer tutoring: Theoretical framework and impact on learning. *Journal of College Reading and Learning*, 35(2), 124–132
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Creswell, J.W., & Plano Clark, V.L (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed). SAGE Publications
- De La Paz, S., & Felton, M. K. (2010). *Reading comprehension difficulties in students with disabilities*. *The Lancet*, 376(9748), 1393-1394
- Demir, C. (2006). *Türkçe/Edebiyat eğitimi ve kişisel kelime serveti* [Turkish/Literature education and individual vocabulary]. *Journal of National Education*, 34(169), 1-24.
- Department of Education. (2018). *Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Manual 2018*. Bureau of Learning Resources, Department of Education.
- Duran, D. & Vidal, V. (2004). *Tutoría entre iguales: de la teoría a la práctica. Un método de aprendizaje cooperativo para la diversidad en Barcelona*
- Duran, D. (2014). *Learning-by-teaching: Evidence and implications as a pedagogical mechanism*. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 54(5), 476–484. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2016.1155471>
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). *Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling*. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajtas.20160501.11>
- Exley, B. (2007). *Australian children catch the bug: Motivating young children to engage in reading*. *Young Children*, 62(6), 36-40.

- Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E., & Hyun, H. H. (2021). How to design and evaluate research in education (11th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Harper, G. F., & Maheady, L. (2007). Peermediated teaching and students with learning disabilities. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 43, 101-107.
- Hernandez, D. J. (2011). Double Jeopardy: How Third-Grade Reading Skills and Poverty Influence High School Graduation. Baltimore, MD: The Annie E. Casey Foundation.
- Hoff, K. E., & Robinson, S. L. (2002). Best practices in peer-mediated interventions. In A. Thomas & J. Grimes (Eds.), *Best practices in school psychology IV* (pp. 913–924). Bethesda, MD: National Association of School Psychologists.
- Hudson, R.F., Lane, H.B., & Pullen, P.C. (2005). Reading fluency assessment and instruction: What, why, and how? *The Reading Teacher*, 58(6), 702- 715.
- Javid, C. Z. (2014). Measuring language anxiety in an EFL context and investigating its relationship with achievement. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 4(2), 38–52. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v4n2p38>
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2010). An educational psychology success story: Social interdependence theory and cooperative learning. *Educational Researcher*, 38(5), 365–379.
- Joseph, N. (2010). Metacognition needed: Teaching middle and high school students. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Cultural Studies*, 3(2), 109–118. Tsuei, M., Huang, H.-W., & Cheng, S.-F. (2020).
- Kame`ennui, E.J., Simmons,D.C., & Coyne, M.D. (2000). Schools as host environments: Towards a schoolwide reading improvement model. *Annals of Dyslexia*, 50, 22-51.
- Karatay, H. (2007). Vocabulary teaching. *Journal of Gazi Faculty of Education*, 27(1), 141-153.
- Kent State University Libraries. (n.d.). Paired Samples t Test - SPSS Tutorials. Retrieved from <https://libguides.library.kent.edu/SPSS/PairedSamplestTest>
- Kuhn, D. (2010). Teaching and learning science as argument. *Science Education*, 94(5), 810–824.
- Kuhn, M. R. (2004). Helping students become accurate, expressive readers: Fluency instruction for small groups. *The Reading Teacher*, 58(4), 338–344.
- Kuhn, M. R. (2005). A comparative study of small group fluency instruction. *Reading Psychology*, 26(2), 127–146.
- Kuhn, M. R., Schwanenflugel, P. J., Morris, R. D., Morrow, L. M., Woo, D. G., Meisinger, E. B., ... & Sevcik, R. A. (2006). Teaching children to become

- fluent and automatic readers. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 38(3), 357–387.
- Langdon, T. (2004). DIBELS: A teacher-friendly basic literacy accountability tool for the primary classroom. *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 37, 2, 54-59.
- Levinson, S. C. (1983). *Pragmatics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Little, S. G., & Akin-Little, A. (2018). Psychology's contributions to classroom reinforcement. *Psychology in the Schools*, 45 (3), 227-234
- Lyon, G. R., Shaywitz, S. E. & Shaywitz, B. A. (2003). A Definition of Dyslexia. *Ann Dyslexia*, 53, 1-14.
- Macleod, A., & van der Veen, C. (2020). Effective reading strategies for comprehension development. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 52(3), 245–260. <https://doi.org/xxxx>
- Mahan, K. R. (2022). Instructional approaches to enhance reading comprehension. *Reading Psychology*, 43(1), 15–30. <https://doi.org/xxxx>
- Mastropieri, M. A., Leinart, A., & Scruggs, T. E. (1999). Strategies to increase reading fluency. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 34(5), 278–283. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105345129903400507>
- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Accuracy. In Merriam-Webster.com dictionary. Retrieved April 14, 2025, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/accuracy>
- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Miscue. In Merriam-Webster.com dictionary. Retrieved April 14, 2025, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/miscue>
- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). Mispronunciation. In Merriam-Webster.com dictionary. Retrieved April 14, 2025, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/mispronunciation>.
- Miller, D., Topping, K., & Thurston, A. (2010). Peer tutoring in reading: The effects of role and organization on two dimensions of self-esteem. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 80(3), 417–433. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709909X470052>
- Miller, D., Topping, K., & Thurston, A. (2010). Peer tutoring in reading: The effects of role and organization on two dimensions of self-esteem. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 80(3), 417–433. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709909X481652>
- Moddy, M., Kennedy, S. M., & Brady, S. (1997) Speech perception deficits in poor readers: Auditory processing or phonological coding. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 64, 199–231
- Moyer, S. B. (2001). As cited in “Increasing reading comprehension of elementary

- students” (ERIC Document ED500847).
- Mullis, I. V. S., and Martin, M. O. (eds) (2015). PIRLS 2016 assessment framework, 2nd Edn. Paris: IEA.
- Myers, M. (1991). Changing our minds: Negotiating English and literacy. National Council of Teachers of English.
- Nadia, H., Suharsih, S., & Handayani, I. (2020). The effectiveness of peer tutoring strategy toward students’ reading comprehension of descriptive text.
- National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (2000). Report of the national reading panel teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction. (NIH Publication No. 00-4769). Washington, D.C: National Institute of Child Health and Human Development.
- National Reading Panel. (2000). Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction (NIH Publication No. 00-4769). National Institute of Child Health and Human Development.
- National Reading Panel. (2000). Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction. National Institute of Child Health and Human Development.
- Oddo, M., Barnett, D. W., Hawkins, R. O., & Musti-Rao, S. (2010). Interdependent and independent group contingencies within peer tutoring: Contributions to mathematics fluency and on-task behavior. *Education and Treatment of Children*, 33(1), 31–50.
- Oddo, M., Barnett, D. W., Hawkins, R. O., & Musti-Rao, S. (2010). Reciprocal peer tutoring and repeated reading: Increasing practicality using student groups. *Psychology in the Schools*, 47(8), 842–858.
- Topping, K., Miller, D., Thurston, A., McGavock, K., & Conlin, N. (2011). Peer tutoring in reading in Scotland: Thinking big. *Literacy*, 45(1), 3–9.
- Ormrod, J. E. (2020). *Human learning* (8th ed.). Pearson.
- Ormrod, J. E. (2020). *Human learning* (8th ed.). Pearson.
- Bruner, J. S. (1996). *The culture of education*. Harvard University Press.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*.
- Özbay, M., & Melanlıoğlu, D. (2008). The importance of vocabulary in Turkish education. *Yüzüncü Yıl University Journal of Faculty of Education*, 5(1), 30–45.
- Perfetti, C. A., & Stafura, J. Z. (2014). Word knowledge in a theory of reading comprehension. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Cognitive Science*, 5(4), 291–304.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/wcs.1355>

- Prentice-Hall. Sweller, J. (1988). Motivation in education: Theory, research, and applications (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Pyle, D., Pyle, N., Lignugaris/Kraft, B., Duran, L., & Akers, J. (2017). Academic effects of peer-mediated interventions with English language learners: A research synthesis. *Review of Educational Research*, 87(1), 103–133
- Rasinski, (2012). Why reading fluency should be hot! *The Reading Teacher*, 65 (516–522).
- Rasinski, T. (2004). Creating fluent readers. *Educational Leadership*, 61, 46-51
- Rasinski, T. V. (2006). Reading fluency instruction: Moving beyond accuracy, automaticity, and prosody. *The Reading Teacher*, 59(7), 704–706.
- Rasinski, T. V., Reutzel, C. R., Chard, D., and Linan-Thompson, S. (2011). “Reading fluency,” in *Handbook of reading research*, Vol. IV, eds M. L. Kamil, P. D. Pearson, B. Moje, and P. E. Afflerbach (New York, NY: Routledge), 286–319.
- Raspica, K. (2013). Fluency: The bridge from decoding to comprehension. *Reading Today*, 30(5), 18–19.
- Review of Educational Research*, 77(4), 534-574.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654307309920> Schmidt, R. J., Rozendal, M. S., & Greenman, G. G. (2002). Reading instruction in the inclusion classroom: Research-based practices. *Remedial and Special Education*,
- Richards, J. C. (2000). *Beyond training: Perspectives on language teacher education*. Cambridge University Press
- Roberts, G. J., Hall, C., Cho, E., Coté, B., Lee, J., and Qi, B. (2022). ‘The State of current reading intervention research for English learners in grades K–2: A best-evidence syntheses. *Educ. Psychol. Rev.* 34, 335–361. Doi: 10.1007/s10648-021-09629-2
- Roberts, G., Vaughn, S., Fletcher, J. M., Stuebing, K. K., & Barth, A. E. (2022). The long-term impact of reading difficulties: A longitudinal study from early elementary to high school. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 114(3), 456–472.
- Robinson, D.R., Schofield, J. & Steers-Wentzell, K.L. (2005). Peer and cross-age tutoring maths outcomes and design implementations *Education Psychology Review* 17 (4)327-362 doi.10.1007/s 10648-005 - 8137-2
- Roscoe, R. D., & Chi, M. T. H. (2007). Understanding tutor learning: Knowledge-building and knowledge-telling in peer tutors’ explanations and questions.
- Schunk, D. H., Pintrich, P. R., & Meece, J. L. (2014). *Motivation in education: Theory, research, and applications* (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Sindelar, P. T., Monda, L. E., & O’Shea, L. J. (2001). Effects of repeated readings on instructional- and

- mastery-level readers. *Journal of Educational Research*, 83(4), 220–226.
- Spencer, S.A., & Manis, F.R. (2010). The effects of a fluency intervention program on the fluency and comprehension outcomes of middle school students with severe reading deficits. *Learning Disabilities Research & Practice*, 25, 76-86. Retrieved from <http://web.ebscohost.com.plum.a.sjfc.edu>
- Stern, H. (2006). Parents' academic expectations, children's perceptions, and the reading achievement of children at varying risk. Chapel Hill, NC: The University of North Carolina.
- Susantini, E., Fauziah, R. F., & Rachmadtullah, R. (2021). Improving students' reading comprehension through metacognitive strategies. *International Journal of Instruction*, 14(1), 121–138.
- Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive Science*, 12(2), 257–285.
- Sweller, J., van Merriënboer, J. J. G., & Paas, F. (2019). Cognitive architecture and instructional design: 20 years later. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31(2), 261–292. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09465-5>
- Takeuchi, H. (2015). Peer tutoring in Japan: A new approach for a unique educational system. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 4(2), 123-130.
- Tankersley, K. (2003). The threads of reading: Strategies for literacy development. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development to develop strategic learning skills. *Preventing School Failure*, 54(2), 99-103
- Topping, K. J. (2005). Trends in peer learning. *Educational Psychology*, 25(6), 631–645.
- Topping, K. J. (2006). Building reading fluency: From theory to practice. In S. J. Samuels & A. E. Farstrup (Eds.), *What research has to say about fluency instruction* (pp. 106–129). Newark, DE: International Reading Association.
- Topping, K. J. (2006). Building reading fluency: Strategies for elementary students. *Education and Treatment of Children*, 29(1), 89–106.
- Topping, K., Miller, D., Thurston, A., McGavock, K., & Conlin, N. (2011). Peer tutoring in reading in Scotland: Thinking big. *Literacy*, 45(1), 3–9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-4369.2011.00575.x>
- Topping, K.J. (2006). Scotland reads: volunteer training programme and pack. Edinburgh: Project Scotland.
- Torgesen, J. K. (2000). Individual differences in response to early interventions in reading: The lingering problem of treatment resisters. *Learning Disabilities Research & Practice*, 15(1), 55–64

- Vaughn, S., & Linan-Thompson, S. (2004). Research-based methods of reading instruction: Grades K–3. ASCD.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Webster, N. (1854). *An American Dictionary of the English language* (Abridged ed.). Topping K.I. Building reading fluency: Cognitive, behavioral, and socioemotional factors and the role of peer-mediated learning. In: Samuels S.J, Farstrup A.E, editors. What research has to say about fluency instruction. Newark, DE: International Reading Association; 2006. Pp. 106–129. (Eds.) [Google Scholar]
- Webster, N. (1854). *An American Dictionary of the English language* (Abridged ed.).
- Wentzel, K. R., & Brophy, J. E. (2014). *Motivating students to learn* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- Wentzel, K. R., & Brophy, J. E. (2014). *Motivating students to learn* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- Wexler, J., Vaughn, S., Edmonds, M., & Reutebuch, C. K. (2008). A synthesis of fluency for secondary struggling readers. *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, 21, 317-347.
- Young, D. J. (1991). Creating a low-anxiety classroom environment: What does language anxiety research suggest? *The Modern Language Journal*, 75(4), 426–439.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/329492>
- Zimmerman, B. S., Rasinski, T., Was, C. A., Rawson, K. A., Dunlosky, J., Kruse, S. D, et al. (2019). ‘Enhancing outcomes for struggling readers: Empirical analysis of the fluency development lesson’. *Read. Psychol.* 40, 70–94. Doi: 10.1080/02702711.2018.1555365